

A framework for inclusive student-centred higher education

Elena Marin and Roeland van der Rijst

2.1 Evidence based components

There is an increasing awareness among educational researchers, faculty, students, and academic leadership that contemporary higher education programs should facilitate all students and therefore need to develop inclusive student-centred pedagogies (Korthals Altes et al., 2024; Stentiford & Koutsouris, 2021; Trinidad, 2020). Due to globalisation and widening access to higher education programs student populations diversify (Geertsema & van der Rijst, 2021). Teaching faculty are exploring new teaching approaches to give all students a voice in class and beyond. The increasing awareness of the strengths of inclusive teaching are amplified by the multiple global crises, which present various challenges to higher education institutes (van der Graaf et al., 2021). Among these challenges are the rapid digitalisation of education and the amplification of previously muted and suppressed voices. This digital transformation has heightened the awareness that traditional face-to-face teaching models may not be suitable for all students, particularly those who are underprivileged and underrepresented. In response to this evolving landscape, educators must adapt their teaching methods and curricula, giving attention to voices that have been historically undervalued. Even now higher education is back to on-campus teaching, the awareness that we need to foster conducive and inclusive teaching environments stays. But what evidence based knowledge do we have which competences faculty need to develop in order to create inclusive and conducive learning environments in our higher education programs?

Implementing inclusive student-centred pedagogies that address the needs, aspirations, and ambitions of all students, irrespective of their background or identity, can help rectify these disparities. Such approaches ensure that every voice is heard through various channels and that students are regarded as equal partners in their education. This call for educational reform is underscored and promoted by the European Union through initiatives like university alliances and European agencies that advocate for inclusion, and also by the United Nations through the Sustainable Development Goals. The pedagogical role of faculty should evolve towards fostering an inclusive and equitable learning environment where all students can achieve academic success. This necessitates enhancing inclusive student-centred teaching practices and supporting faculty to develop their understanding of their voice and agency in higher education (Kusters et al., 2024; Whittaker & Montgomery, 2014).

In response to the aforementioned challenges in higher education, inclusive student-centred pedagogies call on stakeholders to establish effective support structures and processes for both faculty and students. The lack of inclusive student-centred pedagogies in current higher education practices often manifests as a conflict between student agency and faculty control (Reeve, 2009). To address this conflict, educational scholars advocate for stronger inclusive student-centred pedagogies that empower students as equal partners (Cook-Sather et al., 2021; Schuetz, 2008; Ottenhoff et al., 2024; Zepke et al., 2010). As any educational reform, this also involves informing and supporting faculty about designing supportive learning environments (Wang et al., 2025) and providing feedback on course design, instructional practices, engagement opportunities, attitudes, tools, and assessment methods (Katsampoxaki-Hodgetts, 2022; Stevens et al., 2024; Van der Rijst et al., 2019). Admiraal and colleagues (2019) emphasize the need to integrate advanced technologies that may transform higher education by enabling more personalised and inclusive learning experiences and at the same time can help tailor education to individual students' needs, and through enhancing inclusivity. Another key aspect is related to the way higher education institutions can address cultural and social barriers and start fostering a culture of inclusion, tackling biases, and ensuring that all students feel valued and supported (Lee et al., 2020). It is important to take into consideration the fact that students with special education needs, from underprivileged social and cultural backgrounds, or underrepresented identity groups

often face specific challenges, such as inclusion into mainstream classrooms and misunderstanding of their needs by faculty members (Efthymiou & Kington, 2017; Mamah et al., 2011; Morina, 2016). Not least, some higher education institutions may face challenges such as faculty members' lack of knowledge, skills, experience, and confidence in implementing inclusive practices (Taylor & Thompson, 2021). Institutional barriers, including policies, and resource constraints, can also hinder inclusivity and therefore the main drive of this European-wide project, COALITION, was to support faculty in higher education to change current pedagogies for the benefits of student learning. The project aimed to offer teaching faculty a space for academic and personal support and development so that they feel ready to face the needs of their diverse student populations. In order to produce educational content and implement processes and tools to support faculty members, first an analysis was conducted to understand which competencies faculty need to develop inclusive student-centred pedagogies.

2.2 Faculty competence framework

Before providing ideas and tools to navigate the various dimensions of inclusive student-centred pedagogies in higher education teaching practise and providing material for shifting practice towards inclusive teaching, we need a lens to look at teaching practices and the competencies of faculty. Therefore, we first needed to develop a framework based on current practices in our universities.

2.2.1 Method of development

The framework for inclusive student-centred pedagogies was developed in a study into the perceived needs and experiences of teaching faculty and students at European universities (COALITION, 2023). Data was collected at six universities in Greece, Latvia, Romania, Spain, Sweden, and The Netherlands. Through online questionnaire surveys to teaching faculty ($n=264$) and to students ($n=548$) a quantitative description of the needs and experiences of inclusive teaching in higher education was performed. The questionnaire surveys took into consideration both institutional context and individual perspectives. The survey consisted of 46 statements, and participants rated them on a 5-point Likert-type scale from "strongly agree" (1) to "strongly disagree" (5). The questionnaires for both teaching faculty and students focused on four main topics: (1) Accessibility and resources that faculty can use to facilitate inclusion; (2) Faculty willingness to support inclusive student-centred approaches; (3) Curricular adjustments by faculty focussing on inclusive teaching approach (curriculum design, teaching method, and assessment); and (4) Faculty ability and concerns in order to facilitate active learning with diverse students. The survey instrument was piloted and used to identify any expected competencies among faculty members involved in inclusive student-centred pedagogies, as well as their faculty development needs across various teaching, learning, and assessment methods. In order to get an in-depth understanding of the survey results semi-structured interviews were conducted with teaching faculty and students. These interviews shed light on faculty intentions, actions, and expectations regarding inclusive teaching. The interview data was coded and then the results were categorised into re-occurring themes. Participation in the study was voluntary, and the research protocol was approved by the institutional review boards for research ethics. The analysis of survey and interview data lead to the construction of a framework of faculty competencies for inclusive student-centred pedagogies in higher education.

2.2.2 Description of the framework

The final framework consists of five dimensions, which encompass the accessibility and resources provided faculty can use to support inclusion in both face-to-face and online activities. Additionally, it addresses the commitment of faculty to adopt inclusive pedagogy approaches and implement curricular adjustments to support these methods. And furthermore, the framework emphasis that faculty should promote the active learning and engagement for all students, aiming to create an inclusive educational environment that accommodates diverse learning needs and approaches.

Figure 2.1: Framework of faculty competence for inclusive student-centred pedagogies in higher education

2.2.3 Affordances for face-to-face activities

The first dimension aims at dealing with *affordances for face-to-face activities* that faculty can use to facilitate inclusion and is divided into four categories:

- *Learning environments* targeting creating inclusive standards for interaction within the community at the beginning of the semester to establish an atmosphere of inclusiveness and staying mindful of unseen obstacles that could disrupt a fair learning environment.
- *Faculty development support* is organised by higher education institutes, for example in the form of a teaching & learning centre, faculty development centre, or educational centre of expertise which organises the provision of support for teaching and learning and also enables access to units that provide technological support and education research.
- *Architectural facilities* pay attention to access for all, for example through wheelchair access, lifts with braille displays, modular desks, and a variety of classroom spaces for group work as well as individual work. All to reduce barriers to adopting inclusive pedagogies.
- *Equipment and technological support* is adapted to the needs of the student and the learning resources are adapted to the social, cultural, and cognitive needs of students.

2.2.4 Affordances for online activities

The second dimension switches the focus to *affordances for online activities* for inclusive practice. Four categories were distinguished:

- *Learning environments* that are built on inclusive standards for online interaction with the teaching faculty and online and on-campus peers, and support the development of a community at the beginning of the semester to establish an atmosphere of inclusiveness and staying mindful of unseen barriers that could disrupt an equitable online learning environment;
- *Faculty development* support which provides pedagogical and technological support specific to online teaching.
- *Technological facilities and equipment* are adapted to online teaching (e.g., sound quality, video quality, connectivity quality) that allow to adopt inclusive pedagogies during learning activities and also favouring group work.
- *e-Learning resources* that are adapted to the social, cultural, and cognitive needs of students, favouring students to collaborate as equal partners in the online learning environments.

2.2.5 Faculty beliefs and willingness

The third dimension focusses on *faculty beliefs and willingness* to support inclusive student-centred approaches has four categories which all target faculty values:

- *Developing awareness* about students learning needs, interests, and patterns.
- *Embracing diversity* in the classroom and the unit and university community
- *Willingness to adapt* to students' different ways of learning.
- *Encouraging perspective-taking* in the classroom based on non-judgmental approaches to discussing cultural, social, racial, gender or religious or any other type of identity.

2.2.6 Pedagogical design competence

The fourth dimension emphasizes faculty's *pedagogical design competence* to support the inclusive student-centred pedagogies, and has a set of four categories emerged for the analysis of the data:

- *Designing for flexible learning* which flexible learning objectives that can be adapted to the needs of each student; including learning activities that foster inclusive participation; adapting teaching to cater for diverse students' needs.
- *Designing with a variety of approaches* designing learning activities that take into account learning differences in various modes (e.g., oral, written, online, face-to-face) and creating group learning activities that allow students to collaborate in an inclusive community of learning (e.g., peer feedback activities, project-based learning, challenging the taking for granted assumptions and values).
- *Designing for student autonomy* empowers students' progressive autonomy and control regarding self-regulation and learning products.
- *Continuous professional training* to develop the repertoire for teaching in an inclusive way.

2.2.7 Assessment design competence

The fifth dimension deals with *assessment design competence* to support the inclusive pedagogy approach. Faculty need to develop the competence to:

- *Design for variation of assessment techniques* taking into account learning differences in various modes (e.g., oral, written, online, face-to-face) and provides opportunities for students to take control over their learning and use those assessment techniques.

- *Flexible time for assessment* provides opportunities to adapt the assessment time to the needs of the students or adapt the moment of the assessment.
- *Continuous professional training* to design and use inclusive assessment techniques in various modes and moments.

2.2.8 Managing active learning and engagement

The last dimension of inclusive student-centred pedagogies emphasized faculty competence to in-class managing *active learning and engagement* of all students by providing:

- *Providing feedback* in a variety of modes (e.g., oral, written, online, face-to-face, individual, group) and recognizing the barriers to students' participation and engagement. Facilitating discussion among students so that different perspectives are shared.
- *Mentoring students* during their learning process to take charge of their learning and develop appropriate self-regulation skills.
- *Time management skills* assist in managing the workload while approaching inclusive pedagogical approaches.
- *Managing various interactions* is the ability to teach in an inclusive environment by creating opportunities for interaction among diverse learners, for example through peer learning and by actively supporting students who require communicative technologies (e.g., Braille, sign language, online readers) and by preventing labelling others as having additional needs.

2.3 Conclusion

We described the framework for faculty competence in inclusive student-centred pedagogies which was developed in a study on the needs and experiences of teaching faculty and students at European universities. The framework highlights faculty willingness to purposefully design teaching approaches and assessment to cater to diverse students' needs, indicating a proactive engagement for inclusive teaching. In the interviews faculty showed willingness to adjust teaching and assessment methods to take into account student differences and ensuring that all students have an equal opportunity to demonstrate their learning. An interesting finding was that faculty were willing to encourage students to engage in discussions and share their perspectives and ideas for the learning environment and activities. This forms a basis to develop student-centred pedagogies. Furthermore, the framework provides a structure to develop opportunities for faculty to develop their competence for inclusive student-centred pedagogies. In conclusion, faculty in higher education have affordances to engage in inclusive teaching in both on-campus and online activities and are willing to make curricular and assessment adjustments. Next step is to better understand how we can support faculty in developing their teaching and how we can foster their continuous professional development. Continued efforts will undoubtedly lead to a more inclusive and equitable higher education experience for all students.

2.4 References

- Admiraal, W., Post, L., Guo, P., Saab, N., Makinen, S., Rainio, O., Vuori, J., Bourgeois, J., Kortuem, G., & Danford, G. (2019). Students as future workers: Cross-border multidisciplinary learning labs in higher education. *International Journal of Technology in Education & Science*, 3(2), 85-94.
- COALITION (2023). *Needs analysis of the faculty members concerning inclusive student-centred pedagogies*. Study report. Bucharest: Romania.
- Cook-Sather, A., Hong, E., Moss, T., & Williamson, A. (2021). Developing new faculty voice and agency through trust-

- ful, overlapping, faculty-faculty and student-faculty conversations. *International Journal for Academic Development*, 26(3), 347-359. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1360144X.2021.1947296>
- Efthymiou, E., & Kington, A. (2017). The development of inclusive learning relationships in mainstream settings: A multimodal perspective. *Cogent Education*, 4(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/2331186X.2017.1304015>
- Geertsema, J., & van der Rijst, R. M. (2021). Access and success: rethinking and widening the impact of academic development. *International Journal for Academic Development*, 26(1), 1-6. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1360144X.2021.1876337>
- Katsampoxaki-Hodgetts, K. (2022). The emergence of a new inclusive meta-scientific genre: 'the Bigger Picture'. *Journal of English for Academic Purposes*, 57, 101114.
- Korthals Altes, T., Willemse, M., Goei, S. L., & Ehren, M. (2024). Higher education teachers' understandings of and challenges for inclusion and inclusive learning environments: A systematic literature review. *Educational Research Review*, 43, 100605. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.edurev.2024.100605>
- Kusters, M., de Vetten, A., Admiraal, W., & van der Rijst, R. M. (2024). Developing Scenarios for Exploring Teacher Agency in Universities: A Multimethod Study. *Frontline Learning Research*, 12(2), 1-27. <https://doi.org/10.14786/flr.v12i2.1419>
- Lee, S. J., Jahng, K. E., & Kim, K. (2020). Light and shade of multicultural education in South Korea: Analysis through Bourdieu's concept of capital. *Journal for Multicultural Education*, 14(2), 149-161. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JME-11-2019-0081>
- Mamah, V., Deku, P., Darling, S. M., & Avoke, S. K. (2011). University teachers' perception of inclusion of visually impaired in Ghanaian universities. *International Journal of Special Education*, 26(1), 70-79.
- Moriña, A. (2016). Inclusive education in higher education: Challenges and opportunities. *European Journal of Special Needs Education*, 32(1), 3-17. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08856257.2016.1254964>
- Ottenhoff-de Jonge, M., van der Hoeven, I., Gesundheit, N., Kramer, A., & van der Rijst, R. M. (2024). Maturing through awareness: an exploratory study into the development of educational competencies, identity and mission of medical educators. *Medical Teacher*, 46(1), 117-125. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0142159X.2023.2239442>
- Reeve, J. (2009). Why teachers adopt a controlling motivating style toward students and how they can become more autonomy supportive. *Educational psychologist*, 44(3), 159-175. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00461520903028990>
- Schuetz, P. (2008). A theory-driven model of community college student engagement. *Community College Journal of Research & Practice*, 32(4-6), 305-324. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10668920701884349>
- Stentiford, L., & Koutsouris, G. (2021). What are inclusive pedagogies in higher education? A systematic scoping review. *Studies in Higher Education*, 46(11), 2245-2261. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03075079.2020.1716322>
- Stevens, T. M., Day, I. N. Z., den Brok, P. J., Prins, F. J., Assen, H. J. H. E., ter Beek, M., Bombaerts, G., Coppoolse, R., Cremers, P. H. M., Engbers, R., Hulsen, M., Kamp, R. J. A., Koksma, J. J., Mittendorff, K., Riezebos, J., van der Rijst, R. M., van de Wiel, M. J. W., & Vermunt, J. D. (2024). Teacher professional learning and development in the context of educational innovations in higher education: a typology of practices. *Higher Education Research & Development*, 43(2), 437-454. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07294360.2023.2246412>
- Taylor, R., & Thompson, L. (2021). Faculty barriers to inclusive education. *Journal of Faculty Development*, 35(2), 123-136.
- Trinidad, J. E. (2020). Understanding student-centred learning in higher education: students' and teachers' perceptions, challenges, and cognitive gaps. *Journal of Further & Higher Education*, 44(8), 1013-1023. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0309877X.2019.1636214>
- van der Graaf, L., Dunajeva, J., Siarova, H., & Bankauskaite, R. (2021). *Research for CULT Committee – Education and Youth in Post-COVID-19 Europe – Crisis Effects and Policy Recommendations*. European Parliament, Policy Department for Structural and Cohesion Policies, Brussels.
- van der Rijst, R. M., Baggen, Y., & Sjoer, E. (2019). University teachers' learning paths during educational innovation in education. *International Journal for Academic Development*, 24(1), 7-20. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1360144X.2018.1500916>

- Wang, L., de Vetten, A., Admiraal, W. F., & van der Rijst, R. M. (2025). Relationship between perceived learner control and student engagement in various study activities in a blended course in higher education. *Education & Information Technologies*, 30, 2463-2484. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-024-12910-w>
- Whittaker, J. A., & Montgomery, B. L. (2014). Cultivating institutional transformation and sustainable STEM diversity in higher education through integrative faculty development. *Innovative Higher Education*, 39, 263–275. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10755-013-9277-9>
- Zepke, N., & Leach, L. (2010). Improving student engagement: Ten proposals for action. *Active learning in higher education*, 11(3), 167-177. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1469787410379680>

